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QUARTZ MAGNETOMETER-GRADIOMETER

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Abstract

The work is devoted to the description of the design of a magnetometer-gradiometer created on the basis of quartz sensors, which has the ability to carry out synchronous measurements at two points spaced apart in space on a fixed or arbitrarily located "measuring base" ΔL with different distances of these measuring points from each other. The device is designed both for scientific research and special research, and for geophysical work in the field.

Keywords: Magnetic field, magnetic measurements, component and gradient measurements, quartz sensor, quartz magnetometer, gradiometer, digital data.

INTRODUCTION

Quartz magnetic instrumentation has always been a "man-made nanotechnology" in terms of the creation and manufacture of quartz magnetic sensors (QMS) by their inventors and master quartz growers. The uniqueness of the work was that the sensitive element QMS was hung (or twisted) on a quartz thread in various ways, the thickness of which, as a rule, was less than the thickness of a human hair and was about 15 ... 50 microns. Therefore, instruments created with the use and on the basis of such sensors, as a rule, are used mainly in the conditions of magnetic observatories (MO) or in organized stationary observation points during field expeditionary work.

QMS have high metrological characteristics in terms of thermal stability and operation in the process of long-term continuous operation. However, these devices require the presence of certain conditions for their

use, the main of which are: the immobility of installation pedestals for QMS, the thermostating of sensors and their dimming during operation, since all QMS structures are built on the basis of photoelectric converters (PEC) [1, 2].

Traditionally, in the process of QMS manufacturing, compensation for the non-measurable constituent (NMC) of the Earth's magnetic field induction vector (VMI) is carried out using two compensatory magnets (CM), which are installed on two different sides of the magnetosensitive element (MSE). Each of the CM is selected in such a way that it (its magnetic moment) compensates for half the value of this NMC to enter the variometer into the measuring range. Two CM provide the total magnetic moment (at the point of the QMS installation for each of the components of the VMI) corresponding to the field necessary to compensate for the NMC in the the QMD center, that is, at the installation site of the suspension system with the MSE.

QMS of various types and designs by the authors-inventors from IZMIRAN developed a great many, which were mainly used by various of devices manufacturers as sensors for magnetovariation stations (MVS) [2, 3]. But the designs of quartz gradiometers, due to their complexity, were practically not created. Currently, there are several developments of "magnetic scales" [2], which were used to study various parts "for non-magnetism", and it is also known to develop a two-component gradiometer with a "measuring base" ΔL equal to 10 cm [4].

The paper considers a variant of the design of a two-channel quartz magnetometer based on QMS with PEC, made on the basis of an LED laser emitter (LE), and a gradiometer based on it (QMG). The scheme and design of the magnetic measuring converter (MMC) created on their basis are also considered. This device allows you to measure of the VMI components anywhere without of the NMC compensator rebuilding and without of additional CM using. In this design of the QMS (in contrast to the classical circuit), both CM are absent - their functions are performed by two coils for the initial (current) installation (CI) of MSE in the operating state and a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) controlled by a microcontroller (MC), which serves to automatically enter the sensor of the device into the measuring range.

The proposed version of the device allows measuring not only of the Earth magnetic field (EMF) variations, but also (using the DAC) to fix the full value of the field of the VMI measured component. It is de-

signed to build of modern MVS, which are used for research in the field and expeditionary conditions, as well as for carrying out special work. The created version of the magnetometer design allows to simplify of the QMS design, abolishing some traditional elements of the PEC, and also, using a laser beam as a PEC synchronizer, to implement a variable "measuring base" ΔL of various lengths and directions.

INSTRUMENT DESIGN

The functional diagram of QMG is shown in Fig. 1A. This figure shows the layout of two separate measuring channels of the MMC and, through laser synchronization of both PEC, the formation of gradiometer "measuring base" ΔL (when fixing the field gradient and its variations) between these measuring channels. Both measuring channels are built according to an identical scheme. Each of the QMS (S1 and S2) is built of the following main elements and parts: a magnetosensitive element (MSE), a reflecting mirror (RM), which together are suspended (fixed) using a quartz thread (QT) (shown in Fig. 1A) with a thickness of 25 microns on a quartz frame (QF), made of a bar of quartz glass with a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 100 mm.

The QF is installed in a round case with dimensions $\varnothing 100$ mm and a height of 40 mm with feedback (NF) and calibration (CC) coils located on it, which are designed to control the operation of the MSE and enter it into the operating range. The option of installing the QF in a rectangular case with dimensions of 120x40x40 mm is envisaged. The general appearance of the QMS structure is shown in Fig. 1B.

Fig.1. General view of the functional scheme (a) and design of the QMS variants and EU of magnetometer-gradiometer (b).

The feedback coil (**NF**) is designed to stabilize of the MMC operation, and the calibration coil (**CC**) performs two functions - it serves for initial installation and entry into the measuring range of the sensor and is used for periodic calibration of the measuring channel and MMC.

The body of each QMS is fixed with a non-magnetic angle on the pedestal **P1** (**P2**), which is equipped with three alignment legs-screws for alignment in the horizontal plane. In the center of the QMS body opposite the MSE with RM there is a round window-hole with a diameter of 30 mm, which is closed with a glass **G1** (**G2**) 1 mm thick, through which a LE beam falls on the RM.

Opposite the RM (at a distance of 10 mm), a photodiode matrix **PM1** (**PM2**) is installed, which is the main element of the PEC, with the help of which the magnetic field is converted to the angle of rotation of the magnet (RF) and to direct current. The MSE (magnet) is mounted (using a QT) inside a damper made of a C-shaped non-magnetic metal plate (not shown in Fig. 1A). The damper is used to protect the QT and to eliminate system vibrations during of the sensor transportation or in the event of abnormal situations. The suspension design with MSE is classic as in most QMS with the location of the MSE and RM in the center of the QF.

LE elements are located on a rotary device (**RD**), which is fixed on the emitter pedestal (**EP**). EP like P1 (**P2**) is equipped with three alignment legs-screws for alignment in the horizontal plane, and RD is an element of alignment and direction of LE rays in windows G1 and G2 on the RM of both QMS.

The functional circuit of QMG contains two identical MMC that allow independent measurements of the selected component of the VMI. Each of the MMC includes converters connected in series: magnetic field - direct current, current - voltage and voltage - digital code. The MMC has a digital output of the measured data for connection (using a serial **RS-232** interface) to a personal computer (**PC**).

The electronic part of the MMC (electronics unit - **EU**) consists of the following main components, which are powered from an external DC source. The magnetic field-direct current converter is designed on the QMS and PEC basis. The current-to-voltage converter is made on the basis of a DC differential amplifier (**DA**), and the voltage-to-digital code converter is made on the basis of an analog-to-digital converter (**ADC**). All elements of the EU are placed in a metal protective non-magnetic moisture-proof case with a size of 240x165x56 mm.

The EU circuit (see Fig. 1A, B) includes a signal amplifier consisting of three functional nodes: DA, an integrator (**INT**) and a DC amplifier (**DCA**), as well as a control circuit (**CU**), a comparator circuit (**KC**) and a power supply (**PS**) that provides supply voltages to all EU and LE circuits. EU also includes an ADC, a DAC, a control MC, an RS-232 serial converter and an PS.

The DA is made on the basis of a low-noise DCA with MDM transformation. It provides the main amplification of the input signal from the PM. The DA to-

gether with the INT and DCA allows to achieve the required output level of analog voltage for the ADC and performs the functions of a filter with a cut-off frequency of 5 Hz. The use of linear NF in the MMC scheme in the undercompensation mode made it possible to realize with high accuracy the linearity of the transformation and a wide dynamic range of measurement of geomagnetic variations by each measuring channel. The value of this range can be changed programmatically using a controlled microcontroller (MC) and a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) within \pm (1000... 4000) nT.

The CU provides control of the QMS operating modes, its calibration and compensation of the NMC and is controlled from the MC. The CU also controls the operation of the KC at moments when the installation and leveling of the entire device takes place. The comparator circuit is also used in the process of installing the MSE in the measuring range using a DAC, when the QMS are located arbitrarily relative to the plane of the magnetic meridian.

The ADC circuit provides digitization of the analog voltage from the DCA output with a frequency of 100 Hz. At the same time, the analog data of the MMC measuring channel is recorded and visualized on the display of the connected PC with an accuracy of 0.1 nT.

The control MC transmits digital data, as well as the exchange of information and control commands through the serial port with the PC and activates the work of the MMC, sending control commands related to the configuration and verification of the operability of the QMS to the CU. The MK also controls the operation of the DAC during the installation of the QMS of the device at the measuring point - for current compensation of the NMC using CC coils and the introduction of sensors into the measuring range and for their calibration. The value of the current stages of DAC compensation is determined by the value of the QMC measuring range and is set programmatically. The PS circuit is built using DC-DC converters, which are powered from an external DC source with a voltage of 7 to 24 V.

The software for QMG provides the organization of the database, their visualization in the course of the work carried out on the PC display and the ability to process data for use in a format suitable for participation in data collection programs. The measurement results of both measuring channels of the device are displayed on the PC display, where also (with the help of software) the gradient of the magnetic field and its variations are calculated at the pace of the experiment in the selected direction.

When preparing and working with QMG, it is necessary to install both QMS on a flat surface at some distance ("measuring base" ΔL) from each other approximately on the same line and level their pedestals (P1 and P2) in the horizontal plane using levels. Next, install EP with LE and, (after switching on LE) with the help of RD direct laser beams to RM of QMS (as shown in Fig. 1a) sequentially to S1 and S2. Using the software on the PC, start the NMC compensation process sequentially for both the MMC1 and MMC2 measuring channels (while the control of the optimal setting of the measuring range of each of the QMS is monitored using

the PC display). Installation of each of the QMS in the center of the measuring range is carried out with an accuracy not worse than $\pm 10 \dots 20$ nT.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research and experimental work carried out, a new device was created - a quartz magnetometer-gradiometer, which has the ability to synchronously measure two quartz sensors spaced apart in space on a fixed or arbitrarily located "measuring base" ΔA with different distances of QMS from each other.

The technical solution of QMS, MMC and the entire device has distinctive features from all previously created structures. The new construction of the PEC circuit using laser synchronization of measuring channels makes it possible to obtain high stability of work in time (which is important for long-term studies in the MO conditions), as well as good stability of operation when changing the ambient temperature within wide limits (which is important when conducting field and expeditionary work). QMG provides for the possibility of operational digital control of both the parameters of the PEC and the control of all modes of the device automatically.

When using QMG in conjunction with a GPS receiver, a high-precision digital accelerometer-orientator and the necessary software, it becomes possible to use the device anywhere without accurately setting and binding the position of the QMS, that is, to carry out

component and gradient measurements of the VMI selected components.

The design of QMG provides for the possibility of using LE for the PEC in the form of laser pointers. At the same time, it becomes possible in the process of carrying out special or short-term work to install QMS at a much greater distance ("measuring base") from each other, and connect each MMC to a PC for data control and transmission using a serial RS422 interface.

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COMPACT DIGITAL QUARTZ VARIOMETER FOR OBSERVATORIES AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

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Abstract

The work is devoted to the description of a new design of a compact quartz sensor and a magnetometer converter based on it. On the basis of these design solutions, a new device was created - a digital quartz variometer, which is designed both for scientific research and for conducting geophysical work in the field.

Keywords: magnetic field, magnetic measurements, component measurements, quartz sensor, quartz variometer, magnetovariation station, digital data.

INTRODUCTION

Quartz variometers (QV) have always differed markedly from other types of magnetometers in that they have significantly higher characteristics in terms of thermal stability, noise immunity and stable operation over a long period of time. This class of devices is designed to record and study geomagnetic variations. Most magnetic observatories (MO) of Russia, as well as many foreign observatories [1, 2], are equipped with such equipment.

In this paper, a new version of the magnetometer converter (MMC) [3] created on the basis of a compact design of a quartz magnetic sensor (QMS) and a photoelectric converter (PEC) is considered, and a version of the digital quartz variometer (DQV) created on the basis of this MMC is presented.

The proposed version of the QMS design is intended for modern magnetovariation stations (MVS), which are used for work in field and expeditionary conditions, as well as for special research and work in the magnetic observatory (MO) conditions.

QUARTZ VARIOMETER FUNCTIONAL DIAGRAM AND DESIGN

Fig.1 shows the functional diagram of the DQV, which is built on the basis of QMS and MMC. The same figure shows the general view (photo) of the QMS, as well as individual elements of the sensor and PET. The MMC is a closed loop of negative feedback (NF) over a magnetic field (MF). This transformation is called an undercompensation transformation, since part of the magnetic signal remains uncompensated and

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